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ESG-

**DIGITALIZATION OF FINANCIAL MANAGEMENT AS A TOOL FOR
IMPLEMENTING THE ESG STRATEGY OF RUSSIAN ENTERPRISES**

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The development of the economy in the era of Industry 4.0 is characterized by a steady shift towards digitalization of business processes, considered as an inevitable condition for increasing the efficiency, competitiveness and adaptability of enterprises. Russian enterprises, despite institutional and technological limitations, are gradually integrating digital solutions into traditional management models, which is confirmed by the increasing level of business digitalization. At the same time, digital transformation is increasingly moving beyond purely commercial goals and correlates with a broader sustainable development agenda. The purpose of the study is to identify the relationship between the digitalization of financial management and the implementation of the ESG strategy of enterprises. To clarify the understanding that the introduction of digital financial instruments and analytical platforms contributes to the formation of positive external effects, expressed in reducing the environmental burden, improving social conditions and increasing the transparency of corporate activities for investors and other stakeholders. Special attention is paid to the role of digital technologies in integrating ESG indicators into financial planning, budgeting, risk management, and investment decision evaluation processes. The study presents an analysis of the possibilities of digitalization of financial management to take into account non-financial ESG risks in the formation of cash flows and the cost of capital, reduce information asymmetry and transform cost-oriented indicators towards long-term sustainability. As a result of the study, it was found that digital financial solutions are not an auxiliary, but a system-forming element of ESG management, ensuring the practical translation of the ESG strategy into the financial parameters of enterprises. The formulated conclusions confirm that it is through the digital contours of financial management that short-term financial goals are aligned with long-term sustainable development goals, which has a positive effect on the investment attractiveness and strategic sustainability of the business. The results obtained expand methodological approaches to financial management in the context of ESG transformation and can be used in the development of corporate financial and digital strategies.

Keywords: digitalization, ESG transformation, sustainable development, investment attractiveness, cost of capital, financial stability, ESG risks, digital financial instruments, value-based management, corporate ESG strategy.

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McKinsey Global Institute, «

» [9].

George Westerman,

[10], Gregory Vial,

» [11, .121].

.Anandhi Bharadwaj

» [12, .472]. David J. Teece, Maren Peteraf Sohvi Leih

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— Business

Intelligence, Big Data,

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Подход	Ключевые цифровые инструменты	ESG-эффекты (каналы влияния)
Операционный соблюдение стандартов корпоративного управления		
Аналитический улучшение качества инвестиционных и кредитных решений		
Стратегический рост долгосрочной устойчивости и инвестиционной привлекательности		

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-	ERP-	ESG-	-
-	(EVA, ROIC, DCF),	ESG-	-
ESG-	ESG-	(E, S)	ESG-
-	-	(E, S, G)	-
-	-	ESG-	-
-	ESG-KPI	(E, S, G)	-

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-	ERP- , BI- - , ESG-	ESG- - - -	- - - ESG-
-	- - -	ESG-CAPEX OPEX, -	- - -
-	- - - DCF-	WACC NPV, IRR ESG-	- - - ESG-
-	- -	- -	ESG- -
-	ESG- -	ESG- -	- -
-	ESG-KPI -	ESG- -	- ESG -

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([2, 6, 18, 19, 22])

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ESG-	, - - , DCF-	ESG- IRR, WACC	ESG- NPV, - ESG- -
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6. — 2023. — 15. — S2. — EDNARIBKJ.
7. — 2019. — 1(59). — 40-45. — EDNYYIULJ.
8. McKinsey Global Institute. The Age of Analytics: Competing in a Data-Driven World. New York: McKinsey, 2016. — URL: www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/quantumblack/our-insights/the-age-of-analytics (date of the application: 24.02.2026).
9. Westerman G. Leading Digital: Turning Technology into Business Transformation / G. Westerman, D. Bonnet, A. McAfee. — Boston: Harvard Business Review Press, 2014. — URL: globaldigitalization.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/leading-digital-turning-technology-into-business-transformation.pdf (date of the application: 24.02.2026).
10. Vial G. Understanding digital transformation / G. Vial // Journal of Strategic Information Systems. — 2019. — Vol. 28, No. 2. — P. 118–144. — DOI: 10.1016/j.jsis.2019.01.003.
11. Bharadwaj, A. Digital Business Strategy: Toward a Next Generation of Insights. / A. Bharadwaj, O. A. El Sawy, P. A. Pavlou & N. Venkatraman // MIS Quarterly. — 2013. — 37. — 471-482. — DOI: 10.25300/misq/2013/37:2.3.
12. Teece D.J. Dynamic capabilities and organizational agility / D.J. Teece, M. Peteraf, S. Leih // California Management Review. — 2016. — Vol. 58, No. 4. — P. 13–35. — DOI: doi.org/10.1525/cmr.2016.58.4.13
13. Mazzucato M. Mission Economy: A Moonshot Guide to Changing Capitalism / M. Mazzucato. — London: Allen Lane, 2021. — DOI:10.1093/ser/mwac042
14. — 2025. — 6, 3(156). — 10-21. — DOI 10.36871/ek.up.p.r.2025.03.06.002. — EDN LGMSOO.
15. ESG- « » / — 2021. — 16, 12(133). — 185-198. — DOI 10.17803/1994-1471.2021.133.12.185-198. — EDNJQOOVR.
16. — 2022. — 21, 3. — 370-394. — EDNYYCHOH.
17. // : , — 2023. — 1(62). — 161-171. — EDNSIHAXA.
18. ESG- // — 2025. — 11. — 275-278. — EDNBATSCY.
19. // — 2025. — 4. — 184-192. — EDNWAWBIA.
20. — URL: www.weforum.org/reports/digital-transformation-initiative (: 24.02.2026).
21. Warner K.S.R. Building dynamic capabilities for digital transformation / K.S.R. Warner, M. W ger // Long Range Planning. — 2019. — Vol. 52, No. 3. — P. 326–349. — DOI: 10.1016/j.lrp.2018.12.002.
22. // : ; — 2018. — 2(93). — 24-29. — EDNYLVZYX.
23. ESG- // — 2023. — 218. — 32-39. — DOI 10.14451/1.218.54. — EDNHPOIUT.
24. // — 2023. — 13, 2. — 615-636. — DOI 10.18334/vinec.13.2.117125. — EDNRDNGFE.
25. // — 2025. — 9. — 209-219. — EDNZFEMMT.
26. // — 2022. — 12. — 37-45. — DOI 10.26425/1816-4277-2022-12-37-45. — EDNOGLBEP.
27. ESG- ? — URL: journal.ecostandard.ru/esg/test/esg-strategiya-modnyy-trend-ili-rabotayushchiy-instrument-mneniya-ekspertov-i-uchastnikov-rynka/ (: 24.02.2026).

28. . . . ESG- / . . . — 2025. — 7. — . 129-131. — EDN CRAXVM.
29. . . . ESG / . . . — 2024. — 1. — . 42-50. — DOI 10.17586/2310-1172-2024-17-1-42-50. — EDN HFSNVJ.

SPISOK LITERATURY

1. Afanas'ev, M. P. ESG-transformaciya v korporativnom sektore: sistematizaciya global'nogo podhoda / M. P. Afanas'ev, N. N. Shash // Problemy prognozirovaniya. — 2022. — 6(195). — S. 185-197. — DOI 10.47711/0868-6351-195-185-197. — EDN WJPSZH.
2. Izmajlov, M. K. Rol' ESG menedzhmenta v strategii razvitiya predpriyatiya / M. K. Izmajlov // Beneficium. — 2024. — 1(50). — S. 47-53. — DOI 10.34680/BENEFICIUM.2024.1(50).47-53. — EDN ABJKDX.
3. Guzyr', V. V. Innovacionnaya ESG-transformaciya firm kak global'nyj trend ustojchivogo razvitiya / V. V. Guzyr' // Ekonomika i upravlenie innovacijami. — 2022. — 1(20). — S. 33-43. — DOI 10.26730/2587-5574-2022-1-33-43. — EDN EPNEGR.
4. Schwab K. Stakeholder Capitalism: A Global Economy that Works for Progress, People and Planet / K. Schwab. — Hoboken: Wiley, 2021.
5. Solncev, I. V. Strategiya cifrovoj transformacii v promyshlennosti: struktura i celevye pokazateli / I. V. Solncev, E. S. Petrenko // Voprosy innovacionnoj ekonomiki. — 2021. — T. 11, 2. — S. 681-702. — DOI 10.18334/vinec.11.2.112287. — EDN AOTOAR.
6. Litvin, A. Yu. Cifrovaya transformaciya sistem upravleniya biznes-processami v rossijskih kompaniyah / A. Yu. Litvin // Vestnik evrazijskoj nauki. — 2023. — T. 15, 2. — S. 2. — EDN ARIBKJ.
7. Klejner, G. B. Ekonomika ekosistem: shag v budushchee / G. B. Klejner // Ekonomicheskoe vozrozhdenie Rossii. — 2019. — 1(59). — S. 40-45. — EDN YYIULJ.
8. McKinsey Global Institute. The Age of Analytics: Competing in a Data-Driven World. New York: McKinsey, 2016. — URL: www.mckinsey.com/capabilities/quantumblack/our-insights/the-age-of-analytics (date of the application: 24.02.2026).
9. Westerman G. Leading Digital: Turning Technology into Business Transformation / G. Westerman, D. Bonnet, A. McAfee. — Boston: Harvard Business Review Press, 2014. — URL: globaldigitalization.wordpress.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/08/leading-digital-turning-technology-into-business-transformation.pdf (date of the application: 24.02.2026).
10. Vial G. Understanding digital transformation / G. Vial // Journal of Strategic Information Systems. — 2019. — Vol. 28, No. 2. — P. 118-144. — DOI: 10.1016/j.jsis.2019.01.003.
11. Bharadwaj, A. Digital Business Strategy: Toward a Next Generation of Insights. / A. Bharadwaj, O. A. El Sawy, P. A. Pavlou & N. Venkatraman // MIS Quarterly. — 2013. — 37. — 471-482. — DOI: 10.25300/misq/2013/37:2.3.
12. Teece D.J. Dynamic capabilities and organizational agility / D.J. Teece, M. Peteraf, S. Leih // California Management Review. — 2016. — Vol. 58, No. 4. — P. 13-35. — DOI: doi.org/10.1525/cm.2016.58.4.13
13. Mazzucato M. Mission Economy: A Moonshot Guide to Changing Capitalism / M. Mazzucato. — London: Allen Lane, 2021. — DOI:10.1093/ser/mwac042
14. Badaraev, T. D. Razrabotka mekhanizma cifrovoj transformacii: integraciya tekhnologij i biznes-processov dlya povysheniya konkurentosposobnosti organizacij / T. D. Badaraev // Ekonomika i upravlenie: problemy, resheniya. — 2025. — T. 6, 3(156). — S. 10-21. — DOI 10.36871/ek.up.p.r.2025.03.06.002. — EDN LGMSOO.
15. Mazhorina, M. V. ESG-principy v mezhdunarodnom biznese i «ustojchivye kontrakty» / M. V. Mazhorina // Aktual'nye problemy rossijskogo prava. — 2021. — T. 16, 12(133). — S. 185-198. — DOI 10.17803/1994-1471.2021.133.12.185-198. — EDN JQOOVR.
16. Stoyanova, O. V. Strategicheskoe upravlenie kompaniej v usloviyah cifrovoj transformacii: analiz koncepcij, podhodov i metodov / O. V. Stoyanova, T. A. Lezina, V. V. Ivanova // Vestnik Sankt-Peterburgskogo universiteta. Menedzhment. — 2022. — T. 21, 3. — S. 370-394. — EDN YYCHOH.
17. Kravchenko, L. A. Razvitie biznesa v cifrovoj ekosisteme: vozmozhnosti, riski i upravlenie / L. A. Kravchenko, I. A. Troyan // Nauchnyj vestnik: finansy, banki, investicii. — 2023. — 1(62). — S. 161-171. — EDN SIHAXA.
18. Karpekov, M. Innovacionnye ESG-platformy kak strategicheskij drajver cifrovoj transformacii i ustojchivogo razvitiya vysokotekhnologichnyh kompanij / M. Karpekov, A. B. Mottaeva // Ekonomika stroitel'stva. — 2025. — 11. — S. 275-278. — EDN BATSCY.
19. Dzholdosheva, T. Yu. Vliyanie innovacionnyh elementov infrastruktury na ustojchivoe razvitie atomnoj energetiki Rossii / T. Yu. Dzholdosheva, A. B. Mottaeva // Kuznechno-shtampovochnoe proizvodstvo. Obrabotka materialov davleniem. — 2025. — 4. — S. 184-192. — EDN WAWBIA.
20. Iniciativa cifrovoj transformacii. — URL: www.weforum.org/reports/digital-transformation-initiative (data obrashcheniya: 24.02.2026).

21. Warner K.S.R. Building dynamic capabilities for digital transformation / K.S.R. Warner, M. W ger // Long Range Planning. — 2019. — Vol. 52, No. 3. — P. 326–349. — DOI: 10.1016/j.lrp.2018.12.002.
22. Skorev, M. M. Strategicheskaya ustojchivost' v usloviyah cifrovoj ekonomiki: kadrovyy i finansovyy aspekty / M. M. Skorev, T. O. Grafova, S. S. Bakina // Nauka i obrazovanie: hozyajstvo i ekonomika; predprinimatel'stvo; pravo i upravlenie. — 2018. — 2(93). — S. 24-29. — EDN YLVZYX.
23. Alekseev, P. V. Napravleniya vnedreniya ESG-principov v rossijskoj ekonomike / P. V. Alekseev // Ekonomicheskie nauki. — 2023. — 218. — S. 32-39. — DOI 10.14451/1.218.54. — EDN HPOIUT.
24. Cifrovizaciya ekonomicheskikh otnoshenij kak faktor ustojchivogo razvitiya stran / V. I. Abramov, I. V. Abramov, A. V. Putilov, I. Trushinya // Voprosy innovacionnoj ekonomiki. — 2023. — T. 13, 2. — S. 615-636. — DOI 10.18334/vinec.13.2.117125. — EDN RDNGFE.
25. Mottaeva, A. B. Ekologicheskie aspekty strategii razvitiya predpriyatij metallurgicheskoy promyshlennosti / A. B. Mottaeva, O. V. Fokina, I. P. Pryadko // Kuznechno-shtampovochnoe proizvodstvo. Obrabotka materialov davleniem. — 2025. — 9. — S. 209-219. — EDN ZFEMMT.
26. Lopatkova, Ya. A. Cifrovizaciya kak faktor dostizheniya ustojchivogo razvitiya mirovoj ekonomiki / Ya. A. Lopatkova // Vestnik universiteta. — 2022. — 12. — S. 37-45. — DOI 10.26425/1816-4277-2022-12-37-45. — EDN OGLBEP.
27. ESG-strategiya: modnyj trend ili rabotayushchij instrument? — URL: journal.ecostandard.ru/esg/test/esg-strategiya-modnyy-trend-ili-rabotayushchij-instrument-mneniya-ekspertov-i-uchastnikov-rynka/ (data obrashcheniya: 24.02.2026).
28. Mottaeva, A. B. ESG-principy v marketingovyh strategiyyah sovremennyh kompanij / A. B. Mottaeva, S. D. Maslova // Innovacii i investicii. — 2025. — 7. — S. 129-131. — EDN CRAXVM.
29. Izmajlov, M. K. Tendencii vnedreniya elementov koncepcii ESG v sistemu menedzhmenta otechestvennyh predpriyatij / M. K. Izmajlov, S. V. Pupencova // Nauchnyj zhurnal NIU ITMO. Seriya: Ekonomika i ekologicheskij menedzhment. — 2024. — 1. — S. 42-50. — DOI 10.17586/2310-1172-2024-17-1-42-50. — EDN HFSNVJ.

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